

SUSTAINABLE SOLUTIONS FOR THE ENERGY INDUSTRY

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Impact Objectives

- The SLAGSTOCK project aims to develop innovative and cost-effective high temperature thermal energy storage for concentrated solar power plants based on the valorisation of a steel industry by-product, slag, as heat storage media.
- The RESLAG project aims to valorise steel slag and reuse it as raw material and feedstock to contribute to a circular economy in different industrial sectors, including the concentrated solar power sector.

Supporting renewable energy's continued growth

Dr Javier Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza, from CIC energiGUNE discusses the challenges the European power sector is currently facing and how the SOLAR-ERA.NET Joint Calls projects SLAGSTOCK and the H2020 project RESLAG are working collaboratively to overcome these, to ultimately secure a brighter energy future for Europe

From your perspective, what does the near future look like for the solar power sector in Europe?

Solar-thermal power generation is currently an emerging technology. However, it is a very exciting time for the concentrated solar power (CSP) sector, full of opportunities as it seeks to reach full maturity. A good example of this is the annual increase in the number of publications, conferences and companies involved in the sector. Some of the developments are aiding satisfactory growth, but reaping the full benefits is still an ongoing process.

How will CSP help to address the main obstacles that Europe's solar industry is faced with?

The biggest challenges that Europe is facing in this area need to be addressed at two different levels. Firstly, Europe must optimise the potential in European countries that have the appropriate solar radiation levels. Unfortunately, CSP cannot be successfully exploited everywhere; it requires enough direct solar radiation which is only found in certain areas of Southern Europe. The development of this technology will depend on the societal and economic situations in these countries, which need to be addressed with specific policies.

However, just because CSP cannot be directly exploited in most of continental Europe, the European community cannot assume a secondary position. To take a leading role, Europe must remain at the forefront of technology development. The complexity of this industry leads to a wide range of techno-scientific challenges that can only be addressed by a multidisciplinary approach, from the basic science to the application. This has been the position of Europe in recent years, and will be maintained according to the roadmap of the CSP development.

Can you talk a little about the different countries and regions involved in SLAGSTOCK and RESLAG projects? How have you balanced their different expectations so far?

SOLAR-ERA.NET brings together more than 20 RTD and innovation programmes in the field of solar electricity technologies in the European Research Area. One of the projects funded and initiated through the SOLAR-ERA.NET Joint Calls that I am coordinating is SLAGSTOCK (Low-Cost Sustainable Thermal Energy Storage Systems Made of Recycled Steel Industry Waste), which is a consortium of six EU partners. A related Horizon 2020 project, RESLAG (Turning waste from steel industry into valuable low cost feedstock for energy intensive industry), which I am also coordinating, is formed by 19 partners from seven European countries. The

core activity of the RESLAG project is the valorisation of the steelmaking by-product, slag, in different innovative and high added value applications. The key to obtaining a satisfactory management of this big project is always to keep a continuous feedback with the partners at all levels, covering both technology and management issues. It is essential to create a well-balanced consortium that contains all the key capabilities required on the project. From our experience this is particularly important when the research project contains an element of activity that is difficult to predict from the beginning. Therefore, assembling a well-balanced and competent team for the project is the main guarantee of success.

What is your perspective on communicating the results from the research throughout the duration of the projects?

The communication and dissemination of the project results is one of the main priorities of the RESLAG and SLAGSTOCK projects. Aligned with this idea, it is anticipated that both projects will be able to publicly share the developed technologies in the second half of the project execution period. The organisation of workshops, seminars and events to show the results will be important once the technology demonstrators, under development in SLAGSTOCK and RESLAG projects, are available.

Sustainable solutions for the energy industry

The SLAGSTOCK and RESLAG project consortiums are focusing their efforts on delivering more sustainable options for the energy industry through investigating options for the effective valorisation of an industrial by-product

According to the European Commission the global market for renewable power remains high, with growth in the renewables industry growing rapidly each year. These are exciting times for the renewable energy sector, but there are also many hurdles to be overcome as Europe moves towards a future powered from sustainable sources.

The pan-Europe SOLAR-ERA.NET network was established within an EU Seventh Framework Programme ERA.NET project designed to support innovation and research in the solar electricity generation sector. One of the projects currently funded through SOLAR-ERA.NET is looking at ways to develop an innovative thermal energy storage. SLAGSTOCK (Low-Cost Sustainable Thermal Energy Storage Systems Made of Recycled Steel Industry Waste) is a three-year project that has been under way since mid-2015. The project is investigating the opportunities to revalorise steel slag, a by-product of the steelmaking industry, as a potential thermal storage material.

THE SEARCH FOR IMPROVED STORAGE
SLAGSTOCK Project Coordinator Dr Javier Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza explains that it is much easier and more cost-efficient to store energy in the form of thermal energy than in the form of electrical energy. Currently this storage is done through molten salt, but this comes with a high cost and technical limitations. These are

the obstacles the SLAGSTOCK consortium is hoping to overcome by developing an alternative, cost-effective solution to thermal storage.

One of the important characteristics of the SLAGSTOCK project is that it covers the complete value chain, says Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza, 'from the basic material science, being the characterisation of the steel slag thermo-physical properties and the basic or conceptual design of the addressed single-tank packed bed-type storage solution, to the laboratory-scale technological demonstration, including the construction of a lab-scale thermal storage prototype to validate the developed technology'. This whole-of-production approach is also multidisciplinary, embracing the areas of material science, computational modelling and design, and laboratory prototyping.

It's now nearly two years into the project and Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza is pleased that the team have addressed several basic and conceptual issues: 'We have determined the macroscopic operational and design parameters of the slag-based packed bed storage concept. The proposed design offers a high storage energy density at around 200 Kwh/m³, high operational temperature up to 700° Celsius, high thermal performance and efficiency up to 95 per cent, and a low cost.' He notes that it is important to understand that the cost of the proposed applications is directly

driven by the cost of the storage material, which in this case is a by-product. The team is now preparing a laboratory-scale prototype to enable a detailed experimental operation under realistic conditions. The consortium is now in a position to validate and refine the physical models.

VALORISING STEEL SLAG

SLAGSTOCK is intimately connected to other ongoing EU Horizon 2020 projects, including the RESLAG (Turning waste from steel industry into valuable low cost feedstock for energy intensive industry) project, which is led by CIC energiGUNE, an energy storage research centre in the Basque Country, and is investigating the potential for an effective valorisation of steel slag for a range of applications. Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza is also coordinating RESLAG, which is aiming to develop four different technologies for the slag valorisation in different industrial scenarios. The RESLAG project aims to deliver an experimental demonstration of the investigated slag valorisation concepts by the real construction and operation of different pre-industrial prototypes. These include: Pilot 1: Valuable and critical metal recovery from steel slag such as manganese, chromium and iron; Pilot 2: Waste heat recovery from the steelmaking industry and storage using steel slag as heat storage material; Pilot 3: Innovative heat storage concepts for CSP

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applications based on steel slag; and Pilot 4: Steel slag as feedstock for refractory material production.

‘The valorisation of the steel slag that we are attempting to deliver through RESLAG leads to a drastic cost reduction and to a clear enhancement of the obtained thermal performance,’ Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza says. ‘This approach will open the door for a high temperature storage solution that will be useful in a new generation of CSP production that offers increased operational temperatures and efficiencies.’ The pilots will be built in operating industrial or test facilities to prove the viability of the solutions.

‘The wide scope of the RESLAG and SLAGSTOCK projects presents an inherent difficulty, as they condense four different and independent activities into a single project,’ explains Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza. ‘These projects cover the entire value chain from the basic concept to the demonstration at pilot plant level, and this means that a huge effort in research, development, market analysis and search for final users of the proposed technologies needs to be undertaken.’ He points out that the work undertaken on both projects so far has already shown the potential of slag in all of the proposed applications.

SPREADING THE WORD

One of the major priorities of all the parties involved in these two projects is the effective communication of results. ‘The expected impact of the four applications of slag valorisation is huge because a wide range of industries are addressed,’ Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza says. From his perspective it is vital to both communicate and disseminate the results of the projects to any potential technology developer or final user. It is also at the core of the RESLAG and SLAGSTOCK projects to use open access publications. This ensures the knowledge and results obtained are shared in an open manner, available to everyone that has an interest in this industry.

For Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza, using a wide variety of communication tools is the key to achieving a continuous dissemination of their results, from the main public channels to the specialised forums such as specific researchers or industries. An important development for reaching different industries, even those that are not included in these particular projects, is the formation of an advisory board that further disseminates the knowledge gained. An exhibition of the developed technologies is planned for the second half of project which will happen once the four pilot studies are constructed and under operation, around September 2017.

DELIVERING MANY BENEFITS

This is an exciting phase for the team as they begin to see the results of their efforts over the first stages of these projects. As Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza points out, even if the main users of the developed technologies are specific industries, the benefits of both projects have great significance for the general public. Enabling the reuse of a by-product in the four proposed industrial applications supports the concept of a circular and sustainable economy. ‘Currently around 25 per cent of the total EU slag production, around 200 million tonnes, is not recycled and this is being targeted by the RESLAG and SLAGSTOCK projects.’

Additionally, there are some significant public gains from reducing the amount of energy needed for industrial processing and ultimately a more efficient use of energy sources. ‘In terms of greenhouse gas emission reduction, RESLAG and SLAGSTOCK also represent a noticeable impact,’ says Rodríguez-Aseguinolaza. For example, estimations associated with the heat recovery in the steelmaking industry support reductions of around 70 kg per produced steel tonne.’ As a consequence, these two projects will directly benefit the efforts to make Europe’s future one of renewable power.

Project Insights

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SLAGSTOCK PARTNER COUNTRIES

France • Germany • Spain • Switzerland

RESLAG PARTNER COUNTRIES

Finland • France • Germany • Italy • Morocco • Spain • Switzerland • United Kingdom

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